

Synthesis of 2-methyl, 3-aryl or arylalkyl 5,6-dimethyl or Polymethylene Thieno [2,3-d]-pyrimidine-4-ones*

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Synthesis of 2-methyl, 3-aryl or arylalkyl 5,6-dimethyl or polymethylene thieno [2,3-d]-pyrimidine-4-ones is described. A few compounds showed weak diuretic, hypotensive and anti-inflammatory activity.

SUBSEQUENT to the observation that diverse biological activities are associated with various substituted 4(3H)-quinazolones, some thieno [3,2-d], [3,4-d] pyrimidine-4-ones¹⁻⁴ of the general formulae I, II have been found to exhibit analgesic, anti-inflammatory, diuretic and CNS-depressant activities. Recently 2-mercapto-3, 4-dihydrothieno [2, 3-d]-pyrimidine-4-one (III) and 2-methyl 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 9-hexahydrobenzo-[b]-thieno[2,3-d]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-5-one (IV) have been claimed to be potent hypocholesterolemic⁵ and anti-inflammatory agents⁶ respectively.

In a programme to obtain potent anti-inflammatory diuretic and hypocholesterolemic agents, it was considered of interest to synthesize a series of thiophene isosters of 4(3H)-quinazolones and related compounds and this communication describes the synthesis of 2-methyl, 3-aryl or arylalkyl 5, 6-dimethyl or polymethylene thieno [2,3-d] pyrimidine 4-ones.

Manhas *et al*⁷ reported the formation of a mixture of the cyclic compound V and the open chain amides VI when ortho or meta substituted anilines were used. We too obtained the open chain amides in some cases but only in minor quantities. The absence of NH band in ir spectra of the compounds reported here indicated the formation of the cyclic compound.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The compounds were routinely analysed for C, H, N and were found to give satisfactory values. They were also checked by spectral analysis.

2-Methyl 5, 6-substituted 4-oxo-thieno oxazines: These were prepared according to conventional method by refluxing the appropriate 2-acetylamino-4, 5-substituted thiophene 3-carboxylic acid⁸⁻⁹ (0.008 mole) (Table 1) with freshly distilled acetic anhydride (0.054 mole) for 1 hr. Excess acetic anhydride was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was cooled, filtered, washed with dry hexane and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The compounds are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 1—2-ACETYLAMINO 3-CARBOXY 4,5-SUBSTITUTED THIOPHENES

R ₁	R ₂	m.p.°C
Me	Me	193-4
—(CH ₂) ₃ —	—	205,
—(CH ₂) ₄ —	—	215
—(CH ₂) ₆ —	—	165

TABLE 2—2-METHYL 5,6-SUBSTITUTED THIENO-OXAZINES

R ₁	R ₂	m.p.°C	Yield%
Me	Me	104-5	65
—(CH ₂) ₃ —	—	115	51
—(CH ₂) ₄ —	—	110	70
—(CH ₂) ₆ —	—	105	85

2-Methyl 3, 5, 6-substituted-thieno-[2, 3-d] pyrimidine-4-ones^{10,11}: These were prepared by heating a mixture of the corresponding 2-methyl 5, 6-substituted-4-oxo-thieno oxazines with an appropriate primary amine at 160-170° in an oil bath for 2 to 3 hrs in an atmosphere of nitrogen with occasional shaking. The reaction mixture was extracted with CHCl₃, washed

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TABLE 3 - 2,5,6-TRI METHYL 3-SUBSTITUTED THIENO [2,3-D] PYRIMIDINE-4(3H)-ONES

S. No.	R	m.p.°C	Yield (%)
1	Phenyl	101-2	19
2	<i>o</i> -Fluorophenyl	106-7	21
3	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	185-6	18
4	2,4-Difluorophenyl	112-4	16
5	<i>o</i> -Trifluoromethylphenyl	143-4	12
6	3,5-Di (trifluoromethyl) phenyl	254-5	10
7	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	128-9	24
8	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	103-4	27
9	2,5-Dimethoxyphenyl	111-2	34
10	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	175-6	32
11	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	161-2	50
12	2,4-Dimethylphenyl	108-9	29
13	2,6-Dimethylphenyl	183-4	22
14	5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro 1-naphthyl	204-5	42
15	Benzyl	134-5	25
16	<i>p</i> -Methoxy benzyl	135-6	32
17	3,4-Dimethoxy benzyl	114-5	44
18	2-Phenyl ethyl	97-8	19
19	2- <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl ethyl	115-6	20
20	2-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl) ethyl	87-8	38
21	2-(<i>p</i> -tolyl)-tolyl	150-1	48
22	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	179-80	23
23	3-Trifluoromethyl, 4-chlorophenyl	186-7	19
24	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	104-5	20
25	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	187-8	21
26	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	162-3	19
27	4,6-Dimethyl-2-pyridyl	118-9	15
28	3-Piperidino-1-propyl	Thick oily liquid	60

TABLE 4 - 2-METHYL 5,6-POLYMETHYLENE-3-SUBSTITUTED THIENO [2,3-d] PYRIMIDINE-4(3H)-ONES

S. No.	R	n	m.p.°C	Yield (%)
1	Phenyl	3	155	10
2	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	3	270	49
3	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	3	185	24
4	Phenyl	4	130	22
5	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	4	195	22
6	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	4	150	28
7	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	4	126	10
8	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	4	140	17
9	<i>o</i> -Trifluoromethylphenyl	4	175	10
10	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	4	215	20
11	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	4	185	21
12	β -Diethylaminoethyl	4	Thick syrupy mass	18
13	β -Phenylethyl	4	128	14
14	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylethyl	4	115	29
15	3,4-Dimethoxyphenylethyl	4	132	25
16	Phenyl	5	127	30
17	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	5	180	21
18	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	5	144	36
19	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	5	110	30
20	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	5	124	25
21	<i>o</i> -Trifluoromethyl	5	150	10
22	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	5	230	21
23	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	5	168	40
24	β -Diethylaminoethyl	5	Thick syrupy mass	22
25	β -Phenylethyl	5	122	35
26	β - <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylethyl	5	124-5	42
27	β -3,4-Dimethoxyphenylethyl	5	120	22

with 10% HCl except in case of compounds 27, 28 (Table 3), 12 and 24 (Table 4) which were washed with water only. After drying over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and removal of the solvent, the residue was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using benzene or ethyl acetate as the eluent. Compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 3.

3-(p-Fluorobutyrophenone) 5, 6-dimethyl thieno-[2,3-d]pyrimidine-4(3H)-one (VII): A mixture of the sodium salt of 5, 6-dimethyl-thieno [2,3-d] pyrimidine-4 (3H)-one¹² (1 gm), sodium iodide (0.7 gm) and γ -chloro-p-fluorobutyrophenone (2 ml) in dry DMF (10 ml) was refluxed for 48 hrs. Solvent was removed, water (25 ml) added and the mixture was extracted with CHCl_3 . After drying (anhydrous Na_2SO_4) the solvent was distilled off and the residue purified by chromatography over silica gel using benzene as the eluent. Crystallization with benzene gave a buff coloured crystalline product, m.p. 85-87°, yield 0.3 gm.

3-Diethylcarbamoyl 5, 6-dimethyl thieno-[2, 3-d] pyrimidine-4(3H)-one (VIII): This was likewise prepared by refluxing the sodium salt of 5, 6-dimethyl-thieno[2, 3-d]pyrimidine-4 (3H)-one with diethyl carbamoyl chloride in dry xylene for 10 hrs, m.p. 86°, yield 0.5 gm.

3-Phenyl-2-thio 1-H 5, 6-dimethyl thieno [2, 3-d] pyrimidine 4(3H) one (IX)¹³: Phenyl isothiocyanate (6.0 ml, 0.05 mole) was added to 2-amino-3-carbethoxy 4, 5-dimethylthiophene (10 gm, 0.05 mole) in absolute EtOH (20 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 2 hrs. A crystalline product separated out on cooling which was filtered and recrystallized from alcohol, m.p. 163-65°, yield 12.1 gm (83%).

3-Phenyl-2-methylthio-5, 6-dimethyl thieno [2, 3-d] pyrimidine-4(3H)-one (X): Methyl iodide (1 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred ice-cooled solution of IX (3.5 g, 0.125 mole) in 2 N NaOH (25 ml). After stirring for 4 hrs at room temperature, it was filtered, washed with water and the product crystallised from hot alcohol, yield 2.9 gm (76%).

Preparation of 2-amino-substituted-3-aryl-5, 6-dimethyl or polymethylene thieno [2, 3-d] pyrimidine 4-ones

by heating IX with various secondary amines at 120-60° was not successful.

In Table 3 compound 1 (63 mg/kg/p.o.) showed diuretic activity in rats equal to chlorthiazide (100 mg/kg/p.o.), but compounds 5, 6, 18 and 22 showed weak diuretic activity. Compound 5 also exhibited mild CNS-depressant action. Compound 12 at 5 mg/kg/p.o. produced a fall in blood pressure (45 mm Hg/12'). Compound 19 at 136 mg/kg/p.o. inhibited carrageenin-induced edema by 30% (in mice).

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